

BIR O'LCHAMLI FOKKER-PLANK TENGLAMASI UCHUN TO'G'RI USUL

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Annotasiya. Ushbu maqolada Fokker-Plank tenglamasini Krank Nikolson sxemasiga asoslangan chekli ayirmalar orqali sonli yechish o'rganilgan. Umumiy uch o'lchamli Fokker - Plank tenglamasi Furye usuli yordamida bir o'lchamli Fokker Plank tenglamasiga keltirilgan. Bu yerda noma'lum funksiya 2 ta fazoviy o'zgaruvchiga bog'liq emas deb faraz qilinadi. Fokker-Plank tenglamasi uchun issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasiga tatbiq qilingan Krank-Nikolson sxemasiga asoslangan to'g'ri usul keltirib chiqarilgan buning uchun birinchi va ikkinchi tartibli xususiy hosilalar Teylor qatori yordamida chekli ayirmalarga almashtiriladi va natijada Fokker-Plank tenglamasi chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasiga keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: xususiy hosila, giperbolik tip, chekli ayirma, to'r funksiyasi, vaqt, Krank-Nikolson tipi, silliq yechim, Fokker – Plank tenglamasi, zarrachalar oqimi, burchak .

THE CORRECT METHOD FOR THE ONE-DIMENSIONAL FOKKER- PLANCK EQUATION

Annotation. In this article, the numerical solution of the Fokker-Planck equation based on the Crank-Nicholson scheme is studied. the general three-dimensional Fokker-Planck equation is reduced to the one-dimensional Fokker-Planck equation using the Fourier method. Here, the unknown function is assumed to be independent of 2 spatial variables. For the Fokker-Planck equation, the correct method based on the Crank-Nicolson scheme applied to the heat diffusion equation is derived. For this, the first and second order partial derivatives are replaced by finite differences using the Taylor series, and as a result, the Fokker-Planck equation is reduced to a system of linear algebraic equations.

Key words: special derivative, hyperbolic type, finite difference, grid function, time, Crank-Nicholson type, Newton's method, smooth solution, Fokker-Planck equation, particle flow, angle.

Bu usulda asosan z o'zgaruvchi vaqt sifatida μ o'zgaruvchi esa fazo sifatida qaraladi.

Aytaylik

$Q_- = [-1, 0) \times [Z_{ini}, Z_{fin}]$, $Q_+ = (0, 1) \times [Z_{ini}, Z_{fin}]$ va $Q_0 = \{0\} \times [Z_{ini}, Z_{fin}]$ bo'lsin.

Darhaqiqat, $\sigma \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left[D(\mu) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu} \right]$ diffuziya hadning mavjudligi $\psi|_{Q_-}$ yechimni $f(\mu)$ ga bog'liq ekanini ko'rsatadi va xuddi shunday fikr $\psi|_{Q_+}$ yechim uchun ham o'rinli.

Ta'kidlash joizki ushbu masalani yoki Q_- yoki Q_+ sohada qadamma-qadam yechish uchun, yechimning noma'lum bo'lgan Q_0 sohadagi qiymatlarini aniqlash talab qilinadi.

Q ning chegarasidagi yashil chiziq ψ yechim f va g funksiyalar orqali berilgan nuqtalar to'plamini ifodalaydi.[1]

Boshqa tomondan, $\psi|_{\{(\mu, Z_{ini}); \mu \in [-1, 0]\}}$ oldinga, $\psi|_{\{(\mu, Z_{fin}); \mu \in [0, 1]\}}$ orqaga harakatlangani uchun butun Q sohada qadamma-qadam yurish usulini qo'llab bo'lmaydi. Natijada, qo'yilgan masalani quyidagicha yechish mumkin:

- yoki Q_0 sohadagi yechimning boshlang'ich qiymatidan foydalanib iterativ algoritm yordamida
- yoki ikki o'lchamli Puasson tenglamasini yechish uchun qo'llaniladigan global sxema orqali yechimning (μ_i, z_n) tugun nuqtalardagi taqribiy qiymatlari bir vaqtning o'zida katta chiziqli lekin sparse sistemaning yechimi topiladigan sxema yordamida.

Biz ushbu maqolada ikkinchi usulni ko'rib chiqamiz. Qo'yilgan masala boshlang'ich qiymatli masala bo'lgani uchun uni yechishda oshkormas sonli sxemalardan foydalanish oshkor ko'rinishdagi sxemalardan samaraliroq hisoblanadi. Bir hil vaznli oshkor va oshkormas qismlardan iborat bo'lgan Krank-Nikolson tipidagi sxema butun to'rda qo'llash uchun qulay sxema hisoblanib, bunda sxemaning ko'rinishini o'zgartirish zarur bo'lmaydi.

Bu sxemadan quyidagacha foydalanamiz.

Aytaylik, $1 < I \in N$, $1 < N \in N$ bo'lib, ushbu bir xil taqsimlangan tugun nuqtalarini qaraylik:

$$\mu_i = -1 + (i-1)h \text{ uchun } i \in \{1, \dots, I\}, \text{ va } h = \Delta\mu = \frac{2}{I-1} \quad (2.1.1)$$

va

$$z_n = Z_{ini} + (n-1)k \text{ uchun } k \in \{1, \dots, N\} \text{ va } k = \Delta z = \frac{Z_{fin} - Z_{ini}}{N-1} \quad (2.1.2)$$

bo'lsin.

U holda

$$\mu_1 = -1 < \mu_2 < \dots < \mu_{I-1} < \mu_I = 1 \quad (2.1.3)$$

va

$$z_1 = Z_{ini} < z_2 < \dots < z_{N-1} < z_N = Z_{fin} \quad (2.1.4)$$

bo'ladi.

Natijada quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

- $D(\mu) = 1 - \mu^2$

- $\psi_i^n - \psi$ noma'lum yechimning (μ_i, z_n) to'rt nuqtalardagi taqribiy qiymat bo'ladi:

$$\psi_i^n \approx \psi(\mu_i, z_n) =: \bar{\psi}_i^n$$

- $z_{n+\frac{1}{2}} = z_n + \frac{k}{2}$

- Berilgan $A(\mu_i)$ funksiya uchun $\bar{A}_i = A(\mu_i)$ va $\bar{A}_{i \pm \frac{1}{2}} = A(\mu_i \pm \frac{h}{2})$.

- Berilgan $B(\mu, z)$ funksiya uchun $\bar{B}_i^n = B(\mu_i, z_n)$.

Dastlab issiqlik tenglamasi qo'llaniladigan Krank-Nikolson usuliga asoslanib ushbu

$$\mu_i \frac{\bar{\psi}_i^{n+1} - \bar{\psi}_i^n}{k} \stackrel{o(k^2)}{\approx} \mu_i \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z} \left(\mu_i, z_{n+\frac{1}{2}} \right) \stackrel{o(k^2)}{\approx} \frac{\mu_i}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z}(\mu_i, z_n) + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z}(\mu_i, z_{n+1}) \right) \quad (2.1.5)$$

topamiz.

Endi, $m \in \{n, n+1\}$ uchun ((1) tenglamaga asosan)

$$\mu_i \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z}(\mu_i, z_n) = \bar{W}_i^m - \bar{\alpha}_i^m \bar{\psi}_i^m + \bar{\sigma}_i^m \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left[D(\mu) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu} \right]_{(\mu, z) = (\mu_i, z_m)} \quad (2.1.6)$$

bo'lib, diffuziya hadi quyidagicha diskretlashtiriladi:

1. Agar $i = 1$ bo'lsa $\bar{D}_1 = 0$ bo'lib

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left[D(\mu) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu} \right]_{(\mu, z) = (\mu_i, z_m)} \stackrel{o(h^2)}{\approx} \frac{4\bar{D}_2 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu}(\mu_2, z_m) - \bar{D}_3 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu}(\mu_3, z_m)}{2h} \quad (2.1.7)$$

o'rinli bo'ladi va $r \in \{2, 3\}$ uchun standart markaziy sxema ushbu

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu}(\mu_r, z_m) \stackrel{o(h^2)}{\approx} \frac{\bar{\psi}_{r+1}^m - \bar{\psi}_{r-1}^m}{2h} \quad (2.1.8)$$

bo'ladi.[2]

2. Agar $i \in \{2, \dots, I-1\}$ bo'lsa ikkinchi tartibli standart markaziy sxemaga asosan

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left[D(\mu) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu} \right]_{(\mu, z) = (\mu_i, z_m)} \approx \frac{o(h^2) \bar{D}_{i-\frac{1}{2}} \bar{\psi}_{i-1}^m - \left(\bar{D}_{i-\frac{1}{2}} + \bar{D}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} \right) \bar{\psi}_i^m + \bar{D}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} \bar{\psi}_{i+1}^m}{h^2} \quad (2.1.9)$$

bo'ladi.

3. Agar $i = I$ bo'lsa, bu hol $i = 1$ hol kabi o'rganiladi. Bunda $\bar{D}_1 = 0$ ekanini e'tiborga olgan holda

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \left[D(\mu) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu} \right]_{(\mu, z) = (\mu_I, z_m)} \approx \frac{o(h^2) \bar{D}_{I-2} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu}(\mu_{I-2}, z_m) - 4\bar{D}_{I-1} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mu}(\mu_{I-1}, z_m)}{2h} \quad (2.1.10)$$

bo'lib, $r \in \{I-2, I-1\}$ uchun (3.8) formula qo'llaniladi.

Fokker – Plank tenglamasini chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasiga keltirish.

Yuqorida keltirilgan formulalar yordamida $I \geq 4, N \geq 2$, va I -juft bo'lgan holda quyidagi sxemalarni qurib olamiz

$(i, n) \in \{1\} \times \{1, \dots, N-1\}$ uchun

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(-\frac{\mu_1}{k} + \frac{\bar{\alpha}_1^n}{2} + \frac{\bar{\sigma}_1^n \bar{D}_2}{2h^2} \right) \psi_1^n + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_1^n \bar{D}_3}{8h^2} \right) \psi_2^n + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_1^n \bar{D}_2}{2h^2} \right) \psi_3^n + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_1^n \bar{D}_3}{8h^2} \right) \psi_4^n + \\ & \left(\frac{\mu_1}{k} + \frac{\bar{\alpha}_1^{n+1}}{2} + \frac{\bar{\sigma}_1^{n+1} \bar{D}_2}{2h^2} \right) \psi_1^{n+1} + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_1^{n+1} \bar{D}_3}{8h^2} \right) \psi_2^{n+1} + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_1^{n+1} \bar{D}_2}{2h^2} \right) \psi_3^{n+1} + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_1^{n+1} \bar{D}_3}{8h^2} \right) \psi_4^{n+1} = \frac{\bar{W}_1^n + \bar{W}_1^{n+1}}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.1)$$

$(i, n) \in \{2, \dots, I-1\} \times \{1, \dots, N-1\}$, uchun

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_i^n \bar{D}_{i-\frac{1}{2}}}{2h^2} \right) \psi_{i-1}^n + \left(-\frac{\mu_i}{k} + \frac{\bar{\alpha}_i^n}{2} + \frac{\bar{\sigma}_i^n \left(\bar{D}_{i-\frac{1}{2}} \right)}{2h^2} \right) \psi_i^n + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_i^n \bar{D}_{i+\frac{1}{2}}}{2h^2} \right) \psi_{i+1}^n + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_i^{n+1} \bar{D}_{i-\frac{1}{2}}}{2h^2} \right) \psi_{i-1}^{n+1} + \\ & + \left(\frac{\mu_i}{k} + \frac{\bar{\alpha}_i^{n+1}}{2} + \frac{\bar{\sigma}_i^{n+1} (\bar{D}_{i-\frac{1}{2}} + \bar{D}_{i+\frac{1}{2}})}{2h^2} \right) \psi_i^{n+1} + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_i^{n+1} \bar{D}_{i+\frac{1}{2}}}{2h^2} \right) \psi_{i+1}^{n+1} = \frac{\bar{W}_i^n + \bar{W}_i^{n+1}}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.2)$$

$(i, n) \in \{I\} \times \{1, \dots, N-1\}$, uchun

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_I^n \bar{D}_{I-2}}{8h^2} \right) \psi_{I-3}^n + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_I^n \bar{D}_{I-1}}{2h^2} \right) \psi_{I-2}^n + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_I^n \bar{D}_{I-2}}{8h^2} \right) \psi_{I-1}^n + \left(-\frac{pt}{k} + \frac{\bar{\sigma}_I^n}{2} + \frac{\bar{\sigma}_I^n \bar{D}_{I-1}}{2h^2} \right) \psi_{I-1}^n + \\ & \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_I^{n+1} \bar{D}_{I-2}}{8h^2} \right) \psi_{I-3}^{n+1} + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_I^{n+1} \bar{D}_{I-1}}{2h^2} \right) \psi_{I-2}^{n+1} + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_I^{n+1} \bar{D}_{I-2}}{8h^2} \right) \psi_{I-1}^{n+1} + \left(\frac{pt}{k} + \frac{\bar{\sigma}_I^{n+1}}{2} + \frac{\bar{\sigma}_I^{n+1} \bar{D}_{I-1}}{2h^2} \right) \psi_{I-1}^{n+1} = \frac{\bar{W}_I^n + \bar{W}_I^{n+1}}{2} \end{aligned}$$

(2.2.3)

bo'ladi. [3]

***I* – toq bo‘lgan holda sxemani o‘zgartirish**

Ta’kidlash kerakki, bu holda ustma-ust tushishi kerak bo‘lgan tenglamalar sonini hamda o‘zgaruvchilar sonini hisoblash kerak. O‘zgaruvchilar soni, $I \times N$ tenglamalar soni esa $I \times (N)$; bo‘ladi, bunda (1) va (2) tenglamalarning boshlang‘ich va so‘ngi shartlaridan, I juft bo‘lganda, I ta qiymatlar, ya’ni

$$i = \frac{I}{2} + 1, \dots, I, \text{ uchun } \psi_i^1 = \bar{f}_i \text{ va } i = 1, \dots, \frac{I}{2}, \text{ uchun } \psi_i^N = \bar{g}_i \quad (2.2.4)$$

I toq bo‘lganda $I-1$ qiymatlar, ya’ni

$$i = \frac{I+3}{2}, \dots, I \text{ uchun } \psi_i^1 = \bar{f}_i \text{ va } i = 1, \dots, \frac{I-1}{2} \text{ uchun } \psi_i^N = \bar{g}_i \quad (2.2.5)$$

hisoblash mumkin.

Natijada I juft bo‘lganda tenglamalar soni o‘zgaruvchilar soniga teng bo‘ladi.

I toq bo‘lgan holda tenglamalar soni o‘zgaruvchilari sonidan bitta kam bo‘lib qoladi.

Xulosa o‘rnida aytish mumkinki:

- Agar juft bo‘lsa chiziqli sistema yopiq bo‘ladi.
- Agar I toq bo‘lsa sistema yopiq bo‘lishi qo‘shimcha bitta tenglama zarur bo‘ladi.

$\mu_{\frac{I+1}{2}} = 0$ bo‘lgan holni qaraymiz.

Dastlabki yondashuv sifatida yoki ushbu

$$\psi_{\frac{I+1}{2}}^1 = f(0) \quad (2.2.6)$$

sonli boshlang‘ich shartdan, yoki

$$\psi_{\frac{I+1}{2}}^N = g(0) \quad (2.2.7)$$

sonli yakuniy (ohirgi) shartdan foydalanishimiz mumkin.

Ta’kidlash kerakki, bu ikkita tenglamalardan bittasi tanlab olinishi kerak.

(2.2.6) va (2.2.7) shartlarni tanlash ixtiyoriy bo‘lgani uchun bu approksimatsiya simmetrik bo‘ladi.

Buni quyidagicha isbotlaymiz. (2.2.2) tenglamada $i = \frac{I+1}{2}$ ga mos ravishda $N-1$ ta tenglamalar o‘rniga (2.2.6) va (2.2.7) shartlarni qo‘llab sistemani yopiq bo‘lishini ta’minlaydigan ya’ni $N-2$ ta tenglamalarni qaraymiz. Ushbu yangi to‘plamni hosil qilish uchun, $\mu = 0$ da (1) tenglama $z = [z_{ini}, z_{fin}]$ uchun quyidagi ko‘rinishni oladi:

$$\alpha(0, z)\psi(0, z) - \sigma(0, z)\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \mu^2}(0, z) = W(0, z). \quad (2.2.8)$$

(3.18) tenglamadan $i^* = \frac{I+1}{2}$ va $n = \{2, \dots, N-1\}$ uchun

$$\bar{\alpha}_{i^*}^n \psi_{i^*}^n - \bar{\sigma}_{i^*}^n \frac{\psi_{i^*-1}^n - 2\psi_{i^*}^n + \psi_{i^*+1}^n}{h^2} = \bar{W}_{i^*}^n \quad (2.2.8)$$

yoki

$$\left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{i^*}^n}{h^2}\right)\psi_{i^*-1}^n + \left(\bar{\alpha}_{i^*}^n + \frac{2\bar{\sigma}_{i^*}^n}{h^2}\right)\psi_{i^*}^n + \left(-\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{i^*}^n}{h^2}\right)\psi_{i^*+1}^n = \bar{W}_{i^*}^n \quad (2.2.9)$$

bo‘lishi kelib chiqadi.

Bu yangi tenglamalar ham hosilalarning ikkinchi tartibli approssimatsiyasiga asoslanadi va shu sababli metodning tartibi $O(h^2) + O(k^2)$ ni saqlaydi.

Shunday qilib, I toq bo‘lgan holda $i = \frac{I+1}{2}$ tanlovga mos (2.2.2) dagi $N-1$ tenglamalar o‘rniga (2.2.10) tenglik orqali berilgan tenglamani hamda (2.2.6) va (2.2.7) shartlar bilan birgalikda yangi $N-2$ ta tenglamani qaraymiz.

Bu yangi tenglamalar ham ikkinchi tartibli chekli ayirmali tenglamalar bilan almashtiriladi.

Taklif va tavsiyalar:

Fokker - Plank tenglamasi uchun qo‘yilgan masala bir qancha olimlar tomonidan sodda hollarda o‘rganilgan, tur xil – xususan to‘g‘ri va iterativ usullar ishlab chiqilgan. Qaralayotgan maqolaning ilmiy yangiligi shunday iboratki, birinchidan Fokker - Plank tenglamasidagi koeffisientlar shu paytgacha faqat bir o‘zgaruvchiga va shuningdek manbasiz holda o‘rganilgan, ikkinchidan ishlab chiqilgan usulning yaqinlashish tartibi umuman o‘rganilmagan. Mazkur maqola yuqorida bayon etilgan ishlarning umumiysi deb bemaol aytish mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Óscar López Pouso and Nizomjon Jumaniyazov. Numerical experiments with the Fokker-Planck equation in 1D slab geometry, *Journal of Computational and Theoretical Transport*, 45, №3, 2016, 184-201.
2. Aziz, A. Kadir; French, Donald A.; Jensen, Soren and Kellogg, Royal Bruce. Origins, analysis and numerical approximation of a forward-backward

parabolic problem, *Mathematical Modelling and Numerical Analysis*, **33**, № 5, 1999, 895-922.

3. Gorbikov, Sergey Pavlovich and Melnikov, Viktor Fedorovich. The numerical solution of the Fokker-Planck equation for modeling of particle distribution in solar magnetic traps, *Mathematical Modeling* 19 № 2 (2007) 112-122.

4. Sheng, Qiwei and Han, Weimin. Well posedness of the Fokker-Planck equation in a scattering process, *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications* 406 № 2 (2013) 531-536.

5. Stein, Daniel and Bernstein, Ira B. Boundary value problem involving a simple Fokker-Planck equation, *Physics of Fluids* 19 № 6 (1976) 811-814.